

Generated Dysarthric Speech: A Supplement, Not a Substitute for Real Data in Dysarthric Speech Recognition - Supplementary Materials

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1. DSR Performance Trend

Fig. 1 clearly shows the performance trend of DSR under different sample combinations. As reported in the article, the more authentic samples there are, the better the DSR performance. However, when only using the synthetic samples, they often do not have a positive effect on performance improvement. Only when the amount of synthetic samples is sufficiently large does DSR performance show a relatively modest improvement. This further confirms that synthetic speech cannot replace authentic speech but can only serve as a supplement to enhance performance.

Figure 1: CER Trends Across Different Groupings

2. Normalization for Acoustic Metrics

To facilitate a more effective comparison of each index and to present the content in a more intuitive manner, we map the values of each index to the interval $[0, 1]$.

Specifically, for the fundamental frequency correlation coefficient, the root mean square error correlation coefficient (RM-C), the MFCC cosine similarity, and the average speaker similarity—originally (ASS) ranging from $[-1, 1]$. We achieve this through a simple linear transformation: $\text{norm_value} = (\text{original_value} + 1) / 2$.

Additionally, we recognize that the range of PESQ spans from -0.5 to 4.5 , with higher values indicating greater similarity between the quality of synthesized speech and the original speech. Consequently, we designate -0.5 as the minimum value and 4.5 as the maximum value, applying maximum-minimum normalization accordingly.

Under typical conditions, the fundamental frequency jitter difference (FOJD) for young individuals generally falls between 0.5% and 1.0% , while the pitch shimmer difference (PSD) for

adults is usually below 3% . Furthermore, the loudness difference (LD) is unlikely to exceed 70 dB. Therefore, during the normalization process, we set the maximum value for fundamental frequency jitter difference at 1% , the maximum for pitch shimmer difference at 3% , and the maximum loudness difference at 70 dB. All minimum values are set to zero, and any values exceeding the maximum are treated as the maximum value. Following this, we perform maximum-minimum normalization.

3. P-value Analysis for Difference of Synthetic and Authentic Speech

Additionally, we performed a P-value analysis on various acoustic metrics, and the results in Table 1 confirm that the differences between the features of synthetic and authentic speech are significant.

Table 1: P-value analysis on metric difference of synthetic and authentic speech

	Speaker ID	1	4	6	8	9	10	12	Overall
Metric	FO	9.7E-27	2.0E-36	3.7E-31	1.1E-32	3.2E-34	8.9E-41	1.9E-26	3.1E-120
	FOJD	1.2E-153	8.0E-96	0	0	0	0	1.9E-162	0
	PSD	7.5E-69	4.3E-59	1.5E-28	3.1E-58	2.5E-32	3.2E-46	4.1E-24	8.3E-234
	LD	1.4E-66	4.2E-52	2.0E-27	8.3E-84	2.2E-25	4.7E-46	8.7E-15	9.0E-167
	p-value	RM-C	2.2E-35	4.6E-49	1.6E-32	2.6E-41	1.7E-44	2.0E-41	1.3E-32
MF-C		1.8E-07	1.2E-04	2.8E-05	2.5E-01	3.1E-05	8.6E-04	2.2E-03	7.9E-02
PESQ		3.4E-134	1.3E-115	5.2E-141	1.1E-131	5.0E-142	5.9E-118	1.8E-120	0
ASS		9.7E-81	1.0E-79	1.4E-70	5.5E-66	5.4E-78	6.3E-74	9.7E-75	0